

STUDY TOWARDS SECONDARY METABOLITES of "TURI" (*Sesbania Grandiflora*, L) II. PRIMARILY QUALITATIVE STUDY of a STEROID in THE ROOT of TURI

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ABSTRACT

Sesbania grandiflora L, member of Fabaceae family, currently known to have several pharmacological activities such as : anti-oxidants, anti-inflammatory and anti-carcinogenic. Few investigations had been carried out to isolate the chemical active constituents of this plant. So far, several compounds like *oleanolic methyl esters*, *cyenin*, and flavonol *glycosides* were found as its major constituents. This investigation is aiming to qualitatively investigate the presence of steroid, one major important class of organic compound, in the root of *S.grandiflora*. Undergoes a series of qualitative testing, including Liebermann-Burchard and Carr-Price test, to the isolated crystal from the root of *S.grandiflora* following by an infrared spectroscopy observation, it was proven that a steroid is present in the samples.

Keywords : Turi, qualitative analysis, root, steroid

INTRODUCTION

Commonly known as a typical tropical zone plants, *Sesbania grandiflora* L or *turi* became a native plants to many Asian countries like India, Malaysia, Thailand, the Philippines and Indonesia. Ecologically grown in the climate with annual temperature range from 24.3 to 26.7 °C, annual precipitation of 4.8 to

22.5 dm³ and pH of 6.6 to 8.5 respectively. Turi is also found to be tolerable to drought, poor soil and water logging conditions (Duke, 1983). *S.grandiflora* leaves and pods were reported palatable and non-toxic for cattle (NAS 1979). Other report mention that while the white flower variety of *S.grandiflora* found to be non-toxic, the purple flower type is highly toxic (Hutagalung 1981).

Fig.1.
Turi Plant (*Sesbania Grandiflora*, L)

Chemical constituent that mainly found in this plant was *oleanolic esters*, *cyanin* (a types of phenolic compounds), and *flavonol glycosides*. Andal and Sulochana (1986) reported that the seed of *S. grandiflora* contains some condensed tannin precursors (cyanidins), leucocyanidin and cyanidin-3-glucoside. This type of compounds was found exhibiting an anti-oxidants, anti-inflammatory and anti-carcinogenic activities (Wang and Mazza, 2002)

Previous investigation by Kalyanagurunathan *et al* (1985) isolating three active molecules : methyl ester of oleanolic acid, nonacosan-6-one and flavonol glycosides type of molecules, kaempferol-3-rutinosides from the flowers of *S.grandiflora*. It was also discovered from this investigation that methyl ester of oleanolic acid could caused a haemolytic effects on sheep and human erythrocytes.

Typical flavonol glycosides also were isolated from *S. grandiflora*. As stated above, from flowers of *S.grandiflora* Kalyanagurunathan *et al* (1985) isolated kaempferol-3-rutinosides. Moreover, Andal and Sulochana (1986) discovered presence of both kaempferol-7-glucoside and kaempferol-3,7-di glucoside in *S.grandiflora* flowers. This type of compound was found actively induced the production of TNF- α , tumour necrosis factor, factor that contributing in cardiovascular and chronic inflammatory diseases (Wang and Mazza, 2002).

Based upon that previous study this paper is aimed to elaborate further study on active constituents, particularly steroid in the root of *S. grandiflora* .

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Plant preparation:

S.Grandiflora was collected from Massulawalie village, Sub-district of Mattirosompe, Pinrang regency in central part of South Sulawesi Province, and taxonomically identified by Mr.Eddyman W.Ferial from Department of Biology, Hasanuddin University-Makassar. After being air-dried the stem bark *S. grandiflora* was cleaned and cut into small pieces.

Preliminary evaluation:

Prior to the isolation works a qualitative evaluation using specific chemical testing was carried out to the fresh plant in order to preliminary assuming the active contents of *S.grandiflora*.

Isolation and Identification:

300 grams of dried root samples was extracted continuously with 3 portions of 500 mL of methanol. Resulted 1500 ml filtrates were then evaporated to provide brown reddish crude methanol extract. These crude methanolic was then extracted in separatory funnel with 5 portion of 50 mL n-hexane to give 250 mL n-hexane filtrate which then evaporated under vacuum to yield 1.9 grams of yellow-greenish n-hexane crude extract. This crude extract was then subjected to column chromatography. Prior to the column chromatography, a series of experiment and orientation was carried out in order to find the proper eluent system for the chromatography. A mixtures of n-hexane / ethyl acetate 1: 9 was found to be the solvent system that gave the best separation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The crude yellow-greenish materials of 1.9 grams were subjected to coloum chromatography with of Silica gel G.60 (30-75) as a stationary phase and n-hexane/ethyl acetate 1: 9 as a mobile phase to result 50 fractions. Among those 50 fractions, only fraction 33 to 36 resulted white crystals of 20 mg with an Rf of 0.43. Those crystals under specific test with a steroid reagent of Liebermann-Burchard and Carr-Price gave a positive results. The result was figure out in Table 1.

Table 1.
Steroid Qualitative Test of *S.grandiflora* Stem Bark

Reagents	Colour Change	Remarks
Lieberman-Burchard	Blue greenish – green – yellow	+++ steroid
Carr-Price	Red – violet	+++ steroid

To confirm the qualitative results an infrared testing was also carried out. The spectrogram clearly showed 16 peak of absorbance. Peak in area of 3415.7 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of a free hydroxyl of the suspected steroid (hydrogen bonding stretching). Furthermore, absorbance peak in 1031.8 cm^{-1} belong to the stretch vibration of C-O, which provoke the assumption of an existing of a hydroxyl group in the desired compound. An aliphatic C-H vibrational stretching peak was appeared at 2918 and 2850.6 cm^{-1} which shown the presence of a methylene (-CH₂-) and mesitylen (-CH) group

respectively. This result also strengthens by the presence of methyl group at 1380.9 cm^{-1} .

Positions of the carbonyl group (secondary form) were showed in the absorbance around 1193.9 cm^{-1} . Strong absorption in the area of 1708.8 cm^{-1} corresponded with an existing of C=O vibrational stretch from a carboxylic acid. In addition, the presence of cyclic *ene* group in the desired compound was shown by a strong absorption intensity in the area of 1641.3 cm^{-1} which corresponding to the cyclohexene and a clear and strong stretching vibration of C=C at 1463.9 cm^{-1} . From the above interpretation it can be summarized that the desired steroid compound contains a group of -OH, C-O, C=O, -CH₃, -CH₂, -CH, C=C, and cyclohexene.

SUMMARY

This research is attempted to qualitatively proven a presence of a steroid in Turi plant

(*S.grandiflora*). The results have shown that positive results were achieved undergoes a series of steroid qualitative test reagent, Liebermann-Burchard and Carr-Price, to a fraction of the samples (fraction 33-36). This result also verified by an infrared observation which clearly shown the presence of several functional groups like : -OH, C=O, -CH₃, -CH₂, -CH and C=C.

In the nearly future our group is going to extend this investigation toward the fully spectroscopic analysis of the containing steroid of Turi in order to predict the exact structure of those steroid.

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